

**Role Of Deputy Channabasappa
in The Development of Education
in The Colonial Rule of Mumbai Karnataka
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ABSTRACT:

This article examines the pivotal role of Deputy Channabasappa in advancing education and the Kannada language during the Colonial Rule in the Mumbai-Karnataka region (Belagavi and Dharwad). Born in 1833, Channabasappa overcame financial hurdles to gain an education, including engineering, at Pune. His dedication to his mother tongue led him to a remarkable career in the education department. As the first principal of the upgraded Teachers' Training College in Belagavi (1864) and later as Deputy Education Inspector, he tirelessly promoted Kannada. He mandated the use of Kannada in teaching and communication, established schools, developed textbooks, and passed circulars to strengthen the language's status, ensuring the region remained distinctly Kannada-speaking despite strong Marathi influence. His efforts laid a strong foundation for the language's growth and eventual administrative recognition.

KEYWORDS:

Deputy Channabasappa, Kannada Language, Education Development, Mumbai-Karnataka, Colonial Rule.

The Tiger of Kannada, the staunch leader of Kannada, Deputy Channabasappa had a very interesting life history. Channabasappa had dedicated his whole life to the rise and development of Kannada language. He was also called as 'light of Kannada'. The sources to know the life and achievements of Deputy Channabasappa are the articles 'Kannadada Huli Channabasappanavaru' by Mudavidu Krishnarayaru, article by Halakatti' Kai.Va.Channabasappa Basalingappaivara Charitreyu" (1930), S.S.Malawad's "Deputy Channabasappa"(1974),M.G. Handral's "Deputy Channabasappa" (1980), R.Y. Dharwadkar's "Hosagannada Arunodaya"(1974), "Kannadada Deepa"(1982) published by Centenary committee of Deputy Channabasappa and also "Kannadada Shakapurusha Channabasappanava-

ru” by the same committee . Along with this the Dr. Balanna Shighalli in his Ph.D thesis entitled” Deputy Channabasappanavara Jeevan matthu Saadhane” (1993), presented the life and achievements of Channabasappa’s, love towards Kannada and his thoughts to Education.

Deputy Channabasappa did humongous work towards education and Kannada language in parts of Belagavi and Dharwad. Channabasappa was born on December 1, 1833 in Dharwad to Basalingappa and Thippavva. He lost his father at the age of 6. Channabasappa’s mother Thippavva took the responsibility and raised her children. Channabasappa had his primary education under the tutelage of Shivarudrayya of Salimath. Shivrudrayya used to teach Kannada, Marathi and Maths in an effective way. Channabasappa was known as tiger in his friend’s group, later fortunately he became the tiger of Karnataka. After completion of his primary education, he desired to learn English. At that time there was scarcity of English schools in Dharwad. Pune and Mumbai were the centres of English learning. He asked his mother regarding his keen interest to go to Pune, but due to financial constraints and cultural differences the idea was rejected by his mother. But Channabasappa was firm in his decision.

Channabasappa’s zeal to learn made him take 3 rupees 10 paisa from his mother’s money box, and he came to his native place Gokak. There he met his cousin Amarappa, but didn’t get any support from him. Later he met his father’s friend Nagappa Girimar who gave him 50 rupees as financial aid with moral support. As there was no commuting facility at that time, he walked 420kms all the way to reach Pune.

In Pune, he met the educationist Govindrao Mahendrakar and with his support joined English Medium School. There with the support of faculty, he showed tremendous advancement in education. With the available scholarship for poor students, he met his educational needs and also invited his mother to Pune itself. Deputy Channabasappa showed his inquisitiveness in Science and Maths. He completed his high school with higher grades. With his desire to learn Engineering, Channabasappa joined Poona Engineering College. Because of his meritorious performance he got a 10 rupees scholarship and graduated with a higher grade. Deputy Channabasappa joined a aluminous, Poona engineering college as a teacher for a short period. Motherland and mother tongue always lingered in his mind. So, in 1855, he returned to Dharwad. For some time, he worked in post office. Later he joined the education department and made a re-

markable difference. By giving importance to Kannada language education his contribution was immense in this field.

CONTRIBUTIONS OF DEPUTY CHANNABASAPPA IN EDUCATIONAL FIELD

With the establishment of DPI (Director of Public Instruction) office in the Mumbai region in 1855 on May 1st, lots of encouragement was received for primary education. Captain J F Lister who was inspector of the education department of south India, set the blueprint for establishing Teacher's Training School, and presented it in the annual report of the public education department of the year 1855-56. To encourage his idea, it was decided to start normal school in Marathi, Gujarati and Kannada regions. Normal school was started at Dharwad in February 1856. Minimum 10 students must be present in such schools. a scholarship of Rs. 3 per month as given to them. Channabasappa was appointed as principal at Dharwad's Primary Teachers Training School in 1861 started by department of education of Mumbai government.

The normal school was shifted from Dharwad to Belagavi in 1861, as the office of the southern educational department inspector's office was at Belagavi. So, Channabasappa started his venture from Belagavi. The scholarship money was raised from rs.3 to 5 after the school was shifted from Dharwad to Belagavi. Earlier it was mandatory that only teachers can learn here, but it was changed and non-teachers were also provided the opportunity. Due to the continuous efforts of Channabasappa, this normal school was upgraded to college in 1864. By default, Deputy Channabasappa became the first principal of this college. This helped him to work in the upliftment of the Kannada language and region. This professional period of Channabasappa was the golden era in the history of Karnataka's cultural period. He worked hard to open the eyes of Kannadigas. His honesty, efficiency, disciplines and planning are the witness to his workmanship. He made each student of the college follow discipline, along with this he also created interest in them about literature, education, history, culture, science, art, religion, agriculture and commerce. At that time Marathi language was of prominence, which was changed by Channabasappa. The students were made compulsorily to read and write in Kannada only, and also to communicate in Kannada only. As there was scarcity of Kannada schools and Kannada books, he started a magazine called "Math Patrike" (1865), through which he made people

realize and understand about Kannada region and language. He also made it clear to British officials that this Mumbai Karnataka region is a pure Kannada speaking region, otherwise it was misunderstood. This shows the confidence of Deputy Channabasappa. During his tenure as Principal, a major development took place, Russell was appointed in the place of Little. This set up a considerable change. With the trust of Russell, Deputy Channabasappa led a strong foundation for the learning of Kannada language. This made Kannada as an official language of this region.

Because of Russell, Channabasappa was appointed as Deputy Education Inspector of Belagavi district (1886). His period as deputy was so popular that the word 'deputy' was added as a prefix to his name.

He made the existence of Kannada language strong by establishing primary schools, training colleges, textbook committees, printing and publication of Kannada books. Deputy Channabasappa made it a point to learn Kannada whoever came in his contact list. He did not go to any moment or occasion to propagate Kannada language.

These all things reveal Channabasappa's flair for Kannada Language. After Channabasappa, Venkat Rango Katti was the interim Principal for Belagavi training college. Later Bhujendraraya Huligol became Principal. In 1867, Venkatrango Katti was appointed as a translator and then he became the Vice Principal there itself. Gangadhar Madivaleswar Turmuri became the assistant Kannada translator. In this way, Belagavi training college produced a troop of Kannada teachers and scholars. Later in 1875, the training college was shifted to Dharwad again.

But the relation of Channabasappa with the college continued the same. Some of the scholars who studied in training college were; M.P.Pujar, Galaganath, Sakkaribaalcharya, S.P.Gavakar, S.B.Joshi, Simpi Linganna, Pandit Kavali, and Mirji Annaraya. Female Training Class was started in 1856 for the education of girls. As an addition to 'Math Patrike', Jeevan Shikshana' became the voice of Kannada.

Deputy Channabasappa had passed 99 circulars in Kannada which are evident of his loyalty to Kannada. For example,

“.....all the letters written by the teachers to me must be in Kannada only”

“..... the core subjects are not taught in Kannada, so its compulsory to teach them in Kannada. Only half marks must not be given.”

Some teachers write letters in Kannada but at the end they write

regards in Hindi this should be stopped. Kannada letters must be in Kannada only.

While counting the numbers some use ‘daha,’bara’, which was fined. Yes, if Kannadigas only will not use Kannada letters and numbers who else to blame? The sense of being Kannadiga, should be there in every Kannadiga, then only we can preserve, protect and develop Kannada language.

For the unification of Karnataka, Deputy Channabasappa was one of the profound workers. A multilinguistic scholar, but a prophet of Kannada. His hardship for Kannada is immortal. Though at that time, Marathi influence was much, he made efforts for the growth of Kannada educational institutions and he was successful in that. He wrote a letter to the Government insisting that mother tongue should be the medium of education. He was just 47 years old when he breathed his last in 1881. He was a role model for everyone. Few regions which were about to be merged in Maharashtra remained in Karnataka, because of his constant efforts. Belagavi and Dharwad were the major places of his work. These two regions became the prominent places of Kannada language and literature.

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